

Systematic comparison of atomistic force fields for the mechanical properties of double-stranded DNA

Carlos Roldán-Piñero,[†] Juan Luengo-Márquez,^{†,‡} Salvatore Assenza,^{*,†,‡,¶} and Rubén Pérez^{*,†,¶}

[†]*Departamento de Física Teórica de la Materia Condensada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, E-28049 Madrid, Spain*

[‡]*Instituto Nicolás Cabrera, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, E-28049 Madrid, Spain*

[¶]*Condensed Matter Physics Center (IFIMAC), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, E-28049 Madrid, Spain*

E-mail: salvatore.assenza@uam.es; ruben.perez@uam.es

Abstract

The response of double-stranded DNA to external mechanical stress plays a central role in its interactions with the protein machinery in the cell. Modern atomistic force fields have been shown to provide highly-accurate predictions for the fine structural features of the duplex. In contrast, and despite their pivotal function, less attention has been devoted to the accuracy in the prediction of the elastic parameters. Several reports have addressed the flexibility of double-stranded DNA via all-atom molecular dynamics, yet the collected information is insufficient to have a clear understanding of the relative performance of the various force fields. In this work, we fill this gap by performing a systematic study in which several systems, characterized by different sequence contexts, are simulated with the most popular force fields within the AMBER family, bcs1 and OL15, as well as with CHARMM36. Analysis of our results, together with their comparison with previous work focused on bsc0, allows us to unveil the differences in the predicted rigidity between the newest force fields, and suggests a road map to test their performance against experiments. In the case of the stretch modulus, we recon-

cile these differences showing that a single mapping between sequence-dependent conformation and elasticity via the crookedness parameter captures simultaneously the results of all force fields, supporting the key role of crookedness in the mechanical response of double stranded DNA.

1 Introduction

The elasticity of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) is a key molecular determinant in the many cellular contexts where this molecule is found. For instance, accomodating dsDNA onto the histone core of nucleosomes comes at a significant mechanical cost^{1,2}, which can be alleviated by intrinsic bending of the sequence^{3,4}. Increasing evidence points also to dsDNA mechanics dependence of transcription factors affinity⁵⁻⁸, thus adding a further layer of complexity to readout mechanisms based on a static description of the system^{5,9-11}. More in general, elasticity affects the DNA response to the mechanical action exerted by proteins and ligands in the most disparate contexts, including genome organization in prokaryotes¹², topology regulation¹³, DNA recombination¹⁴ and toxin-induced double-stranded breaks¹⁵.

Figure 1: Representative snapshot illustrating the pulling protocol. Two opposite forces of magnitude F are applied on the centers of mass (yellow beads) of the C1' atoms (magenta beads) of the second and second-to-last base pairs, separated by a distance d . The forces are aligned along the axis which connects the two centers. The overall elongation L is defined as the sum of helical rises along the ten central base pairs, corresponding to the contour length of the brown zig-zag line depicted in the figure. The backbone of the duplex is represented as green ribbons.

This has prompted an intensive research effort in the experimental characterization of the mechanical properties of dsDNA^{4,16–44}. At length scales larger than 10 nm, the mechanics of the duplex is dominated by the persistence length l_p , which regulates the thermally-induced bending of the molecule. At standard ionic strength, l_p lies in the range^{4,16–22} 45 – 55 nm. At shorter length scales, the flexibility of dsDNA is also dictated by the stretch modulus S and the twist modulus C , which account for the deformability of the molecule in elongation and torsion, respectively. These elastic constants are also of interest for large molecules under the presence of mechanical stress, e.g. forces in the range 1 – 50 pN and torques around 1 – 30 pN nm. Quantitatively, it has been found that S takes typical values within $S = 900 – 1600$ pN^{20–23}, where the variability might be ascribed to the different techniques employed, particularly optical versus magnetic tweezers²³, although a relevant role might be also played by the protocols used for analysis of the force-vs-extension curves. A more uniform

range of values has been instead measured for the twist modulus, $C = 390 – 460$ pN nm^{23–26}. Twist and torsion are also coupled to each other, with dsDNA counterintuitively overwinding upon pulling, as quantified by a negative twist-stretch coupling constant^{23,26–28,45,46} -120 pN nm $< g < -90$ pN nm.

All-atom Molecular Dynamic Simulations (AMDSs) are an excellent tool to investigate the mechanical properties of dsDNA, as they enable the inspection of the microscopic mechanisms underlying the global deformation response⁴⁷. For comparison with experiments, the elongation L and the torsion θ of the molecule as a whole are defined starting from atomistic data, and the elastic constants S , C , g are determined from stress-vs-strain curves^{48,49} or by analyzing the thermal fluctuations of L and θ ^{50,51}. The parm99 force field⁵² in combination with the bsc0 modification⁵³ has been shown to predict elastic constants in good quantitative agreement with the experimental estimations^{46,48,49,54,55}. More recently, further force-field modifications have been proposed

– OL15⁵⁶ and bsc1⁵⁷ – mainly to improve on the prediction of the helical twist, which was slightly underestimated in bsc0⁵³. A thorough comparison of the predicted structural properties has indicated a similar performance of bsc1 and OL15 in capturing the conformational space of dsDNA⁵⁸. Due to their excellent structural agreement with experiments and stability over long simulation times, these modifications have now been accepted as the new standards for simulation of dsDNA. A valid alternative is provided by the CHARMM family of force fields, for which the most up-to-date version – CHARMM36 – has been shown to provide solid predictions for structural properties⁵⁹.

The values of S , C and g predicted by the AMBER and CHARMM force fields have also been found in reasonable quantitative agreement with experiments^{50,57,60–62}. For the persistence length, previous works on bsc1 and OL15 have reported either good quantitative agreement^{57,60} or a significant overestimation of l_p ⁵⁰, while to our knowledge there have been no attempts at estimating l_p from CHARMM36 simulations. Despite the extensive use of these force fields in the literature, there is a lack of comparative studies highlighting the similarities and differences in the predicted elastic properties within the same sequence context. To our knowledge, only Ref.⁵⁰ computes the values of S , C and g by employing bsc1 and OL15 for the same dsDNA fragment, while Ref.⁶⁰ performs a comparison of the values of C and l_p obtained for a 32mer via bsc1 and OL15. Another work focused instead on analyzing a random sequence by employing the bsc0 and bsc1 modifications, as well as CHARMM27 and CHARMM36⁶²; yet, the authors reported a marked instability of the simulations, which prevented computing the elastic constants for CHARMM36⁶².

Future flexibility studies would strongly benefit from a benchmark, where the predictions obtained by the various force fields are assessed in similar conditions and in various sequence contexts, as done previously for the structural features⁵⁸. To meet this need, here we present the results of simulations of various dsDNA sequences performed by using either the bsc1 or

the OL15 modifications with and without constant pulling forces, and compare them with previous reports employing bsc0 on the same set of duplexes^{48,49}. Moreover, we also study the flexibility of the CHARMM36 force field, albeit only in the unperturbed case. The sequences are chosen so as to encompass all the ten distinct base-pair steps^{46,48,49}. We find that the analyzed force fields give similar results for the various elastic constants, although some clear differences are evident. Particularly, the AMBER modifications can be ranked as bsc0 < bsc1 < OL15 according to the predicted value of \tilde{S} , with bsc0 providing the most flexible values and OL15 corresponding to the stiffest molecules. Even though in all cases the elastic constants were found to be in reasonable agreement with experiments for a random-like sequence, in line with previous literature^{50,57,60,61}, the range of values obtained in the full simulation set and the long-time stability of simulations suggest that bsc1 might be a preferred option for future flexibility studies.

2 Methods

2.1 Molecular Dynamics

Following previous work focused on the bsc0 force field^{48,49}, we performed AMDs of the following dsDNA fragments (we write in parentheses the labels that we use in the text to refer to them):

5'-CGCG(AA) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-AA),
5'-CGCG(AC) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-AC),
5'-CGCG(AG) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-AG),
5'-CGCG(AT) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-AT),
5'-CGCG(CG) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-CG),
5'-CGCG(GG) ₅ CGCG-3'	(poly-GG),
5'-GCGCAATGGAGTACGC-3'	(RNG).

The sequences named poly-XY are obtained as pentamers of the step XY, while the sequence RNG contains all possible base-pair step combinations, and has been introduced in the literature to mimic the behavior of long random sequences employed in the experiments⁴⁶. In

all cases, the fragment of interest is sandwiched between two handles in order to minimize end effects⁴⁸.

For each sequence, the dsDNA molecule was built by employing the NAB software within Ambertools19⁶³. The system was then placed in a box of side approximately equal to 9 nm and hydrated with explicit water molecules. In order to ensure overall electrical neutrality, a suitable amount of sodium counterions was added to counterbalance the overall negative charge originating from the phosphate-group moieties. As a control on the relevance of counterion screening, we repeated some simulations by adding 100 mM of NaCl salt. The exact number of ions to be added was determined by following the SLTCAP method⁶⁴ according to the nonlinear reformulation reported in Ref.⁶⁵. For dsDNA, we employed the parm99 force field⁵² with either the bsc1⁵⁷ or the OL15 modifications⁵⁶ as well as the CHARMM36 force field⁵⁹. Water was modelled according to the TIP3P model⁶⁶, while the Joung-Cheatham parameters were employed for the sodium counterions⁶⁷. For some selected cases, we performed simulations also with the OPC model⁶⁸, to check the robustness of the results with respect to the choice of the water force field (Fig. S4 in the Supplementary Material). Long-range electrostatic effects were accounted for by employing Particle Mesh Ewald, while van der Waals interactions were truncated at the real space cutoff (9 Å). We constrained hydrogen-containing bonds by means of the SHAKE algorithm. The integration timestep was set to 2 fs.

Starting from the coordinates provided by NAB, the topology and coordinate files for bsc1 and OL15 were obtained via the tleap software within Ambertools19⁶³. In the case of CHARMM36, the NAB coordinates were used as input in the the web-based CHARMM-GUI tool⁶⁹ to obtain a topology file in AMBER format⁷⁰. The topology file was then further edited to set the ion parameters to the Joung-Cheatham values and to introduce the restraining bonds (see below).

Following standard protocols, the system was first energy-minimized in 5000 steps with re-

straints applied on the duplex followed by other 5000 steps of unrestrained minimization. Then, the system was heated by linearly increasing the temperature from 0 to 300 K in 300 ps at constant volume. This was followed by an equilibration phase in NPT conditions ($T = 300$ K, $p = 1$ atm) of 20 ns. The last snapshot of the equilibration phase was employed as a starting state for the production simulations. In the case of the simulations employing the bsc1 and OL15 force fields, the duplex was stretched by a constant force in the NVT ensemble ($T = 300$ K) according to the protocol introduced in Ref.⁴⁸. This protocol was applied previously in simulations employing the bsc0 modification and focused on the same sequences as in this work⁴⁹, thus enabling to include in our comparison also the results stemming from the use of this older force field. The pulling force was applied between the geometric centers of C1' atoms in the sugars within the second and second-to-last base pairs (yellow beads in Fig. 1). For each sequence, five different production simulations were performed at pulling forces equal to 1, 5, 10, 15 and 20 pN. In order to compute the persistence length, we further considered production simulations in the absence of a pulling force.

In the case of the simulations employing the CHARMM36 force field, we found the sequences to be highly unstable on the microsecond timescale, in agreement with previous reports^{62,71}. To improve stability, we introduced weak interstrand bonds (4 kcal/mol Å², connecting the N1 atom of a purine to the N3 atom of the paired pyrimidine) at the end base pairs to prevent fraying events, as done previously⁷². Despite this restraint, application of the pulling protocol led to disruption of the double helix. Therefore, for the study of this force field we performed production simulations only in the absence of a pulling force, with the addition of further interstrand restraints when needed (see Section 6 in the Supplementary Material for further details).

In the production phase, the simulation time was at least equal to 1 μ s, leading to a cumulated production time of more than 170 μ s. The state of the system was saved every 1000 steps.

All simulations were performed with the GPU-accelerated program pmemd.cuda in the AMBER18 suite⁶³.

2.2 Analysis

The software CPPTRAJ⁷³ was used to extract the structural parameters according to the 3DNA definition⁷⁴. From them, we identified the overall extension L as the sum of the helical rises and the global torsion θ as the sum of the helical twists. In all cases, the handles were discarded from the analysis, so that only the ten central base pairs were considered (Fig. 1). As shown in Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Material for some representative cases, the large simulation time ensured a nice convergence of these variables.

In order to characterize the elasticity of dsDNA, we describe it as an elastic rod which can be stretched and twisted. Thermally-induced bending is neglected at this stage thanks to the reweighting approach described in the next section, which takes advantage of the short length of the molecules to remap the simulations onto pulling forces applied directly to the contour length of the duplex. The energy of the system thus reads

$$E(F) = \frac{1}{2}S\frac{(\Delta L)^2}{L_0} + \frac{1}{2}C\frac{(\Delta\theta)^2}{L_0} + g\frac{\Delta L\Delta\theta}{L_0} - F\Delta L, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta L = L - L_0$ and $\Delta\theta = \theta - \theta_0$, with L_0 and θ_0 referring to the equilibrium values of L and θ in the absence of mechanical stress, while F is the value of the pulling force. Bending fluctuations were instead analyzed in the simulations with $F = 0$, as detailed below.

2.2.1 Free-Energy Perturbation

Since we are interested in the elastic properties of the central fragment, in Eq. (1) we conjugate the force F with the change of the extension ΔL , i.e. of the contour length of the zig-zag line represented in Fig. 1. However, the simulation protocol is actually applying a couple of constant forces along the line joining the centers of the second and second-to-

last base pairs (yellow beads in Fig. 1), so that in the simulations the variable conjugated to F is their euclidean distance d . Hence, the energy \bar{E} regulating the conformational space being explored in the simulations is given by $\bar{E}(F) = E(F) - F(\Delta d - \Delta L)$. In order to properly sample the ensemble corresponding to Eq. (1), we thus employ the Free-Energy Perturbation (FEP) technique⁷⁵. For any observable O , its average value $\langle O \rangle_F$ in the ensemble corresponding to the energy $E(F)$ can be written as

$$\langle O \rangle_F = \frac{\langle O \cdot e^{F(\Delta L - \Delta d)/k_B T} \rangle_{F, \bar{E}}}{\langle e^{F(\Delta L - \Delta d)/k_B T} \rangle_{F, \bar{E}}}, \quad (2)$$

where $k_B T$ is the thermal energy and $\langle \dots \rangle_{F, \bar{E}}$ denotes averaging in the ensemble corresponding to the energy $\bar{E}(F)$. Note that the practical application of the FEP technique relies on the assumption of a significant overlap between the conformational spaces corresponding to E and \bar{E} . In the present case, this is indirectly supported by the observation that the widths of the distributions of L and θ are significantly larger than the shift introduced by the application of different pulling forces (see Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Material for a representative example), thus suggesting that a similar overlap occurs in the ensembles of $E(F)$ and $\bar{E}(F)$ at a given force.

In practice, Eq. (2) implies computing the averages from the simulations by weighting each snapshot according to the Boltzmann weight $\exp[F(\Delta L - \Delta d)/k_B T]$. For each observable and for the corresponding fluctuations, the error was estimated by block analysis⁷⁵. For each block size, the error associated to the sample was computed by bootstrap with 1000 repetitions, where each element was extracted with probability proportional to the corresponding weight. The weight of a block was computed by summing the FEP Boltzmann weights of the snapshots included therein. An example of the error estimation according to block size is reported in Fig. S2 in the Supplementary Information. The final value of the error was obtained by averaging over the last 200 block sizes.

2.2.2 Effective stretch modulus and crookedness stiffness

The average change in extension $\langle \Delta L \rangle_F$ can be computed from Eq. (1), leading to⁴⁸ $\langle \Delta L \rangle_F = L_0 F / \tilde{S}$, where $\tilde{S} = S - g^2/C$ is the effective stretch modulus. Assuming \tilde{S} to be independent of the pulling force, its value can thus be determined from the slope of $\langle \Delta L \rangle_F$ as a function of F .

The crookedness β is a structural parameter quantifying the displacement of the base-pair centers from the helical axis, and is defined as $\cos \beta = L / \sum_i u_i$, where u_i is the center-to-center distance between base pairs i and $i + 1$, and the sum runs over the fragment being analysed⁴⁹. The crookedness stiffness k_β describes the response of β to the pulling force and is defined in analogy to the effective stretch modulus as $\langle \cos \beta \rangle_F = c_0(1 + F/k_\beta)$, where c_0 is the extrapolation of $\langle \cos \beta \rangle_F$ at zero force.

The values of \tilde{S} and k_β were computed by performing a fit of $\langle \Delta L \rangle_F$ and $\langle \cos \beta \rangle_F$ vs F according to the equations above. The associated errors were obtained as $\sqrt{\delta_{\text{ave}}^2 + \delta_{\text{ind}}^2}$, where δ_{ave} is the error arising from the standard least-square minimization applied to the average values and δ_{ind} is the error originated from the indeterminacies of the various points being fitted, estimated according to the protocol described in Ref.⁷⁶. This approach was also used in all the other fits performed in this work.

The values of k_β obtained for the various systems show an approximately exponential behavior when plotted as a function of $\langle \beta \rangle_0$. The function $k_\beta(\langle \beta \rangle_0)$ was thus fitted according to the formula $Ae^{-D \cdot \langle \beta \rangle_0} + B$, where A, B and D are the adjustable parameters⁴⁹. According to a model proposed in the literature⁴⁹, the overall stretching response regulated by \tilde{S} can be ascribed to the combined effect of base-pair centers alignment (decreased crookedness) and stretching of the center-to-center distance u_i :

$$\frac{L_0}{\tilde{S}} = \frac{L_0}{k_\beta} + \sum_i \frac{u_{0,i}}{k_i}, \quad (3)$$

where k_i and $u_{0,i}$ are the elastic constant and zero-force extrapolation determining the re-

sponse of $\langle u_i \rangle_F$ to the pulling force: $\langle u_i \rangle_F = u_{0,i}(1 + F/k_i)$. By following the same procedure as in Ref.⁴⁹, we determined the values of k_i and $u_{0,i}$ for the ten different kinds of steps (Tables S1 and S2 in the Supplementary Material). The predicted value of \tilde{S} was finally computed by means of Eq. (3), where k_β was obtained from $\langle \beta \rangle_0$ via the exponential fit, and the associated indeterminacy estimated by error propagation.

Finally, based on Eq. (3), the contribution to the effective stretching stemming from the crookedness can be estimated as $(L_0/k_\beta)/(L_0/\tilde{S}) = \tilde{S}/k_\beta$.

2.2.3 Computation of force-dependent elastic parameters

Following the theory presented in Ref.⁵¹, the elastic parameters in Eq. (1) can be computed at each value of F by analyzing the fluctuations involving L and θ , thus unveiling the presence of force dependence of the elastic response. For completeness, we report here the formulas employed in this work and derived in Ref.⁵¹:

$$\begin{cases} S = L_0 \frac{k_B T \langle \Delta \theta^2 \rangle_F - F (\langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F \langle \Delta \theta \rangle_F - \langle \Delta \theta^2 \rangle_F \langle \Delta L \rangle_F)}{\langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_F \langle \Delta \theta^2 \rangle_F - \langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F^2} \\ C = L_0 \frac{k_B T \langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_F}{\langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_F \langle \Delta \theta^2 \rangle_F - \langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F^2} \\ g = -L_0 \frac{k_B T \langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F - \frac{F}{2} (\langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_F \langle \Delta \theta \rangle_F - \langle \Delta L \rangle_F \langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F)}{\langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_F \langle \Delta \theta^2 \rangle_F - \langle \Delta L \Delta \theta \rangle_F^2} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

To succinctly characterize the evolution of the elastic parameters with the external force, we perform the linear fits $S(F) = S_0 + F \cdot dS/dF$, $C(F) = C_0 + F \cdot dC/dF$ and $g(F) = g_0 + F \cdot dg/dF$, where the error on the adjustable parameters is computed as in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.4 Computation of elastic parameters in the absence of a force

In the case of the simulations performed with CHARMM36 (i.e. without the presence of a pulling force), the various constants were computed by standard analysis of covariances. Particularly, the effective stretch modulus was obtained as $\tilde{S} = k_B T L_0 / \langle \Delta L^2 \rangle_0$, while the elastic constants S, C, g were obtained setting $F = 0$ in Eq.(4).

Finally, for all the DNA force fields considered, the persistence length l_p was computed by considering the fluctuations of the generalized tilt (τ) and roll (ρ) angles within the framework of the length-dependent elastic model^{54,60}. Particularly, we computed the persistence lengths associated to the two bending modes as $l_p^\tau = \bar{L} / \langle \Delta\tau^2 \rangle_F$ and $l_p^\rho = \bar{L} / \langle \Delta\rho^2 \rangle_F$, where \bar{L} is the contour length of the line joining the base-pair centers of the central fragment, while the generalized tilt and roll were computed considering the first and last base pair within the analyzed fragment. The overall persistence length is then obtained as the harmonic mean of l_p^τ and l_p^ρ , i.e. $1/l_p = (1/l_p^\tau + 1/l_p^\rho)/2$.

3 Results and discussion

We performed simulations employing the AMBER force field parm99, with either the bsc1 or the OL15 modifications. Moreover, we also considered the CHARMM36 force field. To investigate the importance of the sequence, we considered seven different molecules, as reported in the Methods. Note that this same set of sequences has been studied in the past with the bsc0 modification and with the same protocol^{48,49}, enabling throughout this work a direct comparison between the four different force fields in the same context. The sequence RNG contains all possible combinations of base-pair steps, and has been studied in the past to mimic the behavior of long, random sequences employed in single-molecule experiments^{46,48}. The other six sequences are obtained as pentamers of the steps AA, AC, AG, AT, CG or GG, which encompass the ten distinct base-pair steps⁴⁹. We refer to these sequences as poly-XY, where XY is any of the six steps employed to build the pentamers. The endorsement of the results obtained for these sequences as being representative of the underlying step must be however observed with a critical eye, as the flexibility of a step is strongly affected by the neighboring sequences⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹.

For each sequence, after standard minimization and equilibration phases, we performed pulling simulations where two opposite, con-

stant forces are applied to the ends of the molecule (see Methods). We run simulations at different magnitudes F of such forces, namely 1, 5, 10, 15 and 20 pN, as well as in the absence of applied mechanical stress. Due to stability issues (see Section 6 in the Supplementary Material), only the case $F = 0$ was considered in the case of CHARMM36. For the whole set, two external handles were added to the fragment of interest, so as to minimize end effects. In all the subsequent analysis, only the central 10 base pairs were considered.

3.1 The effective stretch modulus depends on the force field

The first elastic parameter investigated is the effective stretch modulus \tilde{S} , which can be obtained from the slope of the average change in elongation $\langle \Delta L \rangle_F$ as a function of the applied force F or, in the case of CHARMM36, by analyzing its fluctuations (Sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.4). As a representative case, in Fig. 2a we report the stress-vs-strain curve for the sequence RNG and the three different AMBER force fields. The slope of the curve is equal to $1/\tilde{S}$, indicating a softer response in the case of bsc0 with respect to the other modifications. In Fig. 2b and in Table 1, we report the results obtained throughout the whole set. In the figure, the shaded grey region corresponds to the experimental values obtained in the literature in pulling experiments of large molecules, where a similar range of forces has been applied. To exclude the possibility of a significant dependence of our results on the TIP3P water model⁶⁶ employed in this work, we repeated some of the simulations using the OPC model⁶⁸, finding small or no changes (Fig. S4 in the Supplementary Material). Similarly, no significant change was observed when comparing counterion neutralizing conditions (considered throughout this paper) with the case of 100 mM of added monovalent salt (Fig. S5 in the Supplementary Material), ensuring the minor relevance of salt screening on our results.

From Fig. 2b and Table 1, a clear pattern emerges for the AMBER family of force fields, according to which the values of \tilde{S} are systemat-

Figure 2: (a) Representative elongation vs force curve for the RNG sequence. The slopes of the linear fits (dashed lines) correspond to \tilde{S}^{-1} . (b) Values of \tilde{S} simulated for each sequence and force field. The shaded regions indicate the experimental range for random sequences²⁰⁻²³ (gray) and phased A-tracts⁴ (pink).

Table 1: Values of \tilde{S} in pN for the various sequences and force fields.

Force Field	RNG	poly-AA	poly-AC	poly-AG	poly-AT	poly-CG	poly-GG
bsc0	837 ± 36	1912 ± 72	943 ± 47	1014 ± 39	846 ± 35	1083 ± 43	658 ± 17
bsc1	1224 ± 53	2065 ± 62	1248 ± 68	1580 ± 69	1310 ± 63	1426 ± 81	980 ± 30
OL15	1320 ± 44	2514 ± 49	1426 ± 65	1960 ± 56	1288 ± 84	1872 ± 55	1500 ± 55
CHARMM36	915 ± 20	1978 ± 34	1098 ± 31	2055 ± 17	540 ± 29	1351 ± 18	548 ± 18

ically ranked in the order $\text{bsc0} < \text{bsc1} < \text{OL15}$, thus outlining a clear difference in the stiffness predicted by the various force fields. In contrast, CHARMM36 can display the stiffest (poly-AG) or the softest response (poly-AT, poly-GG) according to sequence, as well as intermediate values of the elastic constant (RNG, poly-AA, poly-AC, poly-CG).

At a general level, the values obtained for bsc0 and bsc1 mostly lie within the experimentally-known range, while for OL15 they are usually found to be larger. Similarly, also for CHARMM36 some outliers can be observed. While this suggests that OL15 and CHARMM36 might be less precise in capturing dsDNA elongation elasticity, one should take this indication with some caution, as the sequences poly-XY are not directly comparable with long, random sequences usually employed in single-molecule experiments. In this regard,

the most valuable system is provided by the random-like sequence RNG, for which the four force fields predict values of \tilde{S} within the experimental range. Interestingly, in all cases the sequence poly-AA is found to be significantly stiffer than the other molecules (with the exception of poly-AG in the CHARMM36 force field). The most direct experimental comparison for this system is provided by the phased A-tracts reported in a recent study⁴, where pulling by optical tweezers estimated $\tilde{S} = (2400 \pm 220)$ pN. This is in line with the three predictions, with the best quantitative agreement being found for OL15.

Figure 3: (a) Elastic constant associated with crookedness, k_β , as a function of the average crookedness in the absence of applied force, $\langle\beta\rangle_0$. Dashed line is a fit to the function $k_\beta = Ae^{-D\cdot\langle\beta\rangle_0} + B$. (b) Comparison between predicted values of \tilde{S} and results obtained from simulations. (c) Contribution of k_β to the overall stretching response.

3.2 Stretching is determined by crookedness

The crookedness β is a structural parameter characterizing the displacement of the base-pair centers from the helical axis⁴⁹. By definition, larger values of β indicate a more crooked structure, with $\beta = 0$ corresponding to perfectly aligned centers (see Methods for the formal definition). It was proposed that the elongation response of dsDNA to a pulling force can be described as the combined effect of force-induced alignment of the centers and stretching of the center-to-center distance between consecutive base pairs⁴⁹. Intriguingly, this led to a model which, in the case of bsc0, quantitatively predicted the value of \tilde{S} from knowledge of β in the absence of mechanical stress, combined with tabulated values of stiffness of the ten possible base-pair steps combinations. In other terms, this allows predicting the mechanical response from the sequence of the dsDNA fragment and from knowledge of its structure in the absence of applied force.

We employed the extended dataset to check

whether this model is also applicable to the other force fields, or rather it is restricted to bsc0. Following Ref.⁴⁹, we first characterized the stiffness k_β associated to β , which accounts for the energetic cost needed to align the centers (see Methods for the formal definition). In Fig. 3a, we report the values of k_β as a function of the average crookedness $\langle\beta\rangle_0$ obtained in the unperturbed case. Remarkably, the dataset corresponding to the three AMBER force fields (bsc0, bsc1, OL15) can be nicely fitted by a single function of the form $Ae^{-D\cdot\langle\beta\rangle_0} + B$. This phenomenological functional form was proposed in Ref.⁴⁹ for the bsc0 data, and is found here to be able to capture simultaneously the data for the three force fields. The values of the optimized parameters are $A = (0.29 \pm 0.07) \cdot 10^6$ pN, $D = 12.8 \pm 0.7$ and $B = (736 \pm 37)$ pN. This emerging pattern suggests that the difference in rigidity of the various AMBER modifications can be ultimately ascribed to the improved structural features introduced in bsc1 and OL15, at least at the level of the crookedness stiffness. The crookedness constants corresponding to CHARMM36 were not computed

Figure 4: (a) Values of S in the absence of pulling force computed by analysis of fluctuations. The empty diamond for the dataset “Minhas2020” corresponds to simulations performed in the literature with CHARMM27⁶². The shaded region corresponds to the experimental range. Due to the lack of direct experimental determination of S , the shaded region corresponds to the values of \tilde{S} measured in the literature, as in Fig. 2b. (b) Slope of the $S(F)$ curve obtained for the AMBER force fields.

since only simulations of unperturbed molecules were performed in this case.

As the next step, we employed the simulation results for poly-XY to determine the elastic constants associated to the ten distinct base-pair step combinations⁴⁹ (reported in Table S1 in the Supplementary Material). In contrast with the case of k_β , inspection of the step stiffness constants did not reveal a clear pattern in their dependence on the chosen AMBER force field. This further supports the idea that it is the change in structure (i.e. the unperturbed crookedness) which ultimately originates the ranking $\text{bsc0} < \text{bsc1} < \text{OL15}$ observed for \tilde{S} in Fig. 2b and Table 1.

Building on this point, we consider the model from Ref.⁴⁹, which predicts the value of \tilde{S} by considering an effective series of springs involving the crookedness rigidity and the center-to-center distances (see Methods). The value of k_β is computed from the crookedness of the unperturbed system via the empirical exponential function. As for the steps, given the absence of a clear force-field dependence, and with the aim of building a theoretical framework including the three modifications at the same time, we consider for the elastic parameters the averages

of the values obtained for bsc0, bsc1 and OL15 (see Section S2 in the Supplementary Material). In Fig. 3b, we compare \tilde{S} as predicted by the model and the values retrieved directly from the simulations. The close agreement between prediction and numerical results further endorses the universality of the model across the spectrum of the different AMBER force fields.

The comparison between model prediction and simulation results for \tilde{S} can also be used as an indirect proxy to check whether this universality also applies to CHARMM36. In this regard, in Fig.3b we include data points corresponding to CHARMM36, where the predicted value of \tilde{S} was computed assuming that the formula $Ae^{-D \cdot \langle \beta \rangle_0} + B$ holds also for CHARMM36 with the same parameters determined for the AMBER force fields. Although the points are somewhat noisier than the rest of the data, we obtain a remarkable quantitative agreement between predicted and computed values. We stress that these predictions for the CHARMM36 elasticity are based on parameters obtained solely from the analysis of the AMBER simulations. This quantitative agreement thus strongly supports the existence of a single law dictating the stretching elasticity of dsDNA

starting from its crookedness, irrespective of the force field being employed.

Based on the model, we further investigated the contribution of k_β to \tilde{S} ⁴⁹, which was estimated as \tilde{S}/k_β (see Methods) and is reported in Fig. 3c. In most cases, the crookedness is the major responsible for the response to the pulling force⁴⁹, although from a quantitative perspective its contribution is lower for bsc1 and OL15. This is in line with the absence of a pattern in the step stiffness constants which, once combined with the stiffening of k_β induced by the enhanced spontaneous alignment of the centers, results into an overall smaller contribution of the crookedness stiffness.

3.3 Stretch modulus increases with force

The effective stretch modulus \tilde{S} quantifies the net elongation response to the pulling force. Due to a coupling between the extension L and the torsion θ of the duplex, the net elongation change $\langle\Delta L\rangle_F$ induced by F results from the interplay between these two degrees of freedom. Quantitatively, one finds that $\tilde{S} = S - g^2/C$, where S is the stretch modulus, C is the twist modulus and g is the twist-stretch coupling (see Methods for further details).

In Fig. 4a, we report the values of S obtained by fluctuations in the absence of a pulling force. The data show a strong resemblance with the values of \tilde{S} reported in Fig. 2b. This is expected, since the typical values of g and C (see below) provide a small correction when employing the formula $\tilde{S} = S - g^2/C$, thus leaving unchanged the pattern observed above, i.e. the systematic ranking $\text{bsc0} < \text{bsc1} < \text{OL15}$. For completeness, we also report values of S published in the literature^{50,57,61,62}. Particularly, the data labeled as ‘‘Dohnalova2022’’ consider the same sequence for bsc1 and OL15⁵⁰, confirming for a specific case our general observation on the higher rigidity of OL15. Similarly, the dataset ‘‘Minhas2020’’ is also in line with our results, showing that for the same sequence bsc1 is more rigid than bsc0⁶². In this case, also the CHARMM27 force field was studied, yielding a value of S (empty diamond in

Fig. 4a) similar to the one predicted by bsc1. On a more general level, we note that the various results from the literature further support the robustness of our results with respect to the choice of water and ions details, as some of the reported works have employed different conditions as the ones considered here, such as the SPC/E model for water^{50,57}, potassium ions modelled via the Dang model⁵⁰ (at difference with the Joung-Cheatham parameters for sodium employed here)⁵⁰, as well as different concentrations of salt ranging from neutralizing conditions⁵⁷ up to 150 mM⁵⁰.

The description of dsDNA via only two variables is necessarily an effective one, so that the elastic parameters S , C and g are expected to change according to the applied mechanical stress⁵¹. We have recently introduced a theoretical framework which allows to determine the force-dependent values of the elastic parameters by studying their fluctuations in the constant-force ensemble and employed it to analyze the force-dependent behavior of dsDNA and dsRNA⁵¹. For dsDNA, in our previous work we employed the bsc0 data. Here, we study the extended dataset to check the robustness of our conclusions with respect to the force field considered. For completeness, we report in the Methods the formulas derived in Ref.⁵¹ which are employed in the present study (Eq. (4)). Since for CHARMM36 we performed simulations only for $F = 0$ pN, this force field was not included in this analysis.

To characterize the force-induced change in the stretch modulus, we performed a linear fit of $S(F)$, for which the slope dS/dF is reported in Fig. 4b. For all sequences, $dS/dF \geq 0$, indicating that dsDNA stiffens upon pulling, in agreement with our previous report on bsc0⁵¹. Microscopically, this stiffening can be ascribed to the progressive alignment of the aromatic rings of consecutive base pairs due to the action of the force, which increases the strength of stacking interactions⁵¹. This picture is supported quantitatively by the significant correlation ($r \simeq 0.70$) between the change in stretch modulus dS/dF and the change in slide $d\lambda/dF$, as can be observed from Fig. S3 in the Supporting Material. All in all, the present analysis

fully extends to the bsc1 and OL15 force fields our previous findings on the force-induced stiffening of dsDNA⁵¹.

3.4 Twist modulus ranking depends on sequence

Our results for the twist modulus C are reported in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5a, we show the values of C obtained in the absence of a pulling force, together with data collected from the literature^{50,57,60–62}. The agreement with the experimental values (shaded area) is generally good for all the force fields. When considering random-like sequences (first five rows in Fig. 5a), bsc1 yields results quantitatively within the experimental range in several cases (“Various authors”^{57,60,61} and “Velasco2020-32mer”⁶⁰), although other works report larger values of C (“Minhas2020”⁶² and “Dohnalova2022”⁵⁰), while the random sequence RNG studied in this work displayed a softer twist response. The ranking $\text{bsc0} < \text{bsc1} < \text{OL15}$ holds for several sequences (poly-AA, poly-AG, poly-CG, RNG), but is not as general as we found for S . For instance, for poly-AT OL15 is found to be as soft as bsc0, while bsc0 shows the highest twist stiffness in the case of poly-AC. The most peculiar case is provided by poly-GG, for which bsc0 has a much larger value of C than both the other modifications, despite showing enhanced flexibility in the stretching mode (Fig. 4a). This case reflects previous observations on the dependence of rigidity on the elastic mode under consideration^{80,81}. The lack of a general pattern in C is supported by other data from the literature, which show reversed rankings for bsc1 and OL15 (OL15 < bsc1 in Ref.⁵⁰, bsc1 \lesssim OL15 for the 32mer in Ref.⁶⁰). As for CHARMM36, similarly to the case of S , also for C there is no particular tendency when comparing to the AMBER force fields; for instance, CHARMM36 has a markedly stiffer twist response for poly-AG, but enhanced flexibility in the case of poly-AC. Notably, a previous report employing CHARMM27 (empty diamond in “Minhas2020”⁶²) has found a two-fold increase of C as compared to the experimental range.

In Fig. 5b, we report the slope dC/dF to characterize the force dependence of C . We observe virtually no change in the twist modulus, with the exception of the sequence poly-GG, which shows a clear negative slope for all cases. It is worth mentioning that this duplex is the most crooked molecule, for which the force-induced straightening of the spontaneous curvature is likely to induce a softer twist response⁵¹.

3.5 The force fields qualitatively capture the twist-stretch coupling

In Fig. 6 we report the results obtained for the twist-stretch coupling g . In almost all cases, we find that $g < 0$ (Fig. 6a), in agreement with experimental results²⁶. Quantitatively, there is a tendency of all the AMBER force fields to overestimate the magnitude of g with respect to experiments (shaded region in Fig. 6a), as observed in previous work⁴⁸, while CHARMM36 tends to underestimate the coupling. While this feature might be a potential target to address in future refinements of the force fields, such mismatch must be taken with caution, due to the likely dependence of g on the length of the fragment under consideration⁷⁶. Particularly, based on a nucleotide-level coarse-grained model, we have previously reported significant changes of g in the 20-40 base-pairs range⁷⁶, so that such an effect is expected to be further enhanced for the large molecules employed in experiments. In terms of ranking, in analogy to C no clear patterns are present, although one may notice a generic shift of OL15 values towards larger magnitudes of g .

In Fig. 6b, we report the slope dg/dF characterizing the change of twist-stretch coupling with force. For all force fields and all sequences, one has $dg/dF \geq 0$ within error, indicating a weakening of g with the pulling force. Again, this is in line with previous reports on bsc0⁴⁸ and with the experimental literature^{26,28}. As a future direction, it will be an interesting challenge to check the performance of the various force fields in capturing the experimentally-observed sign reversal of g at forces around 40

Figure 5: (a) Values of C in the absence of pulling force computed by analysis of fluctuations. The empty diamond for the dataset “Minhas2020” corresponds to simulations performed in the literature with CHARMM27⁶². The shaded region corresponds to the experimental range. (b) Slope of the $C(F)$ curve obtained for the AMBER force fields.

pN.

3.6 Persistence length is overestimated by all force fields

In Fig. 7 we report the results obtained for the persistence length, computed by analyzing the fluctuations of the generalized roll and tilt angles as defined by the length-dependent elastic model^{54,60}, by considering the global bending of the central decamer of each sequence (see Methods). At a general level, all the force fields tend to overestimate the overall persistence length l_p (Fig. 7a). Remarkably, for the random sequence RNG, CHARMM36 shows the best agreement with experiments (53 ± 1 nm, within the experimental range). To our knowledge, there have been no previous attempts in the literature to compute l_p from atomistic simulations with CHARMM36; hence, whether this observation stands for a general behavior on random sequences will need to be confirmed in future works extending the pool of simulated molecules. We observe no general tendency for the AMBER force fields, for which all possible rankings are present.

It is worth discussing shortly the various outliers. CHARMM36 predicts soft bending for

poly-AC and poly-AT, which we also found to be the most unstable sequences in this force field (see Section 6 in the Supplementary Material). Although we filtered out transient disruptions of the duplex, the weakness of the stacking interactions likely allows conformational changes promoting the thermally-induced bending of the molecule. A second remarkable outlier is poly-GG within the bsc0 modification, for which the persistence length is roughly twice (94 ± 1 nm) the value obtained experimentally for random sequences. This high bending stiffness, together with the large crookedness (Fig.3a) and the small stretching modulus (Fig.4a), is reminiscent of the typical elastic behavior of double-stranded RNA²³, appointing the sequence poly-GG – as described by bsc0 – as an intermediate structure between ideal B-DNA and A-DNA, as suggested previously based on crookedness data⁴⁹. Nevertheless, the twist-stretch coupling of poly-GG is still negative, thus retaining the standard behavior of dsDNA in terms of the positive correlation between extension and torsion, which has instead opposite sign for double-stranded RNA²³.

In Fig. 7b, we focus on the anisotropy of the bending stiffness, considering the persis-

Figure 6: (a) Values of g in the absence of pulling force computed by analysis of fluctuations. The empty diamond for the dataset “Minhas2020” corresponds to simulations performed in the literature with CHARMM27⁶². The shaded region corresponds to the experimental range. (b) Slope of the $g(F)$ curve obtained for the various sequences and force fields.

tence length l_p^ρ , associated to the roll angle (i.e. bending towards the grooves, full symbols in Fig. 7b), and the tilt persistence length l_p^τ , which accounts for bending towards the backbone (empty symbols in Fig. 7b). Note that the overall persistence length l_p is found as the harmonic mean of l_p^ρ and l_p^τ . No patterns are observed when comparing the force fields with respect to each other. Instead, for each sequence and force field, we systematically find that l_p^ρ is larger than l_p^τ , in agreement with previous reports in the literature for fragments of similar length⁸¹. We note that this trend is inverted if one considers local rather than global bending flexibility, for instance at the level of a base-pair step (Fig. S8 in the Supplementary Material), in line with the larger variance of dinucleotide roll vs tilt degrees of freedom observed both in crystal structures⁸² and simulations⁶¹.

Conclusions

In this work, we have performed a systematic comparison of the molecular mechanics of dsDNA as predicted by the most advanced force fields for dsDNA in the AMBER and CHARMM families, including as well the older gold standard provided by the bsc0 modifica-

tion of the parm99 force field. We have found that the global response of the duplex to a pulling force is captured with good precision by all the models, although some clear differences are evidenced.

The three AMBER modifications show similar behavior in the twist modulus and in the twist-stretch coupling, in terms of both their average values and their evolution with the magnitude of the external force being applied. As for the stretching, a clear pattern is observed, according to which the force fields are ranked from the softest to the stiffest as $\text{bsc0} < \text{bsc1} < \text{OL15}$. This feature is perhaps the most prominent difference observed to date between the bsc1 and OL15 modifications, for which previous studies have reported very similar performance in reproducing the structural features of dsDNA⁵⁸. CHARMM36 predicts similar values for stretch and twist moduli when compared to the AMBER force fields, although the difference in flexibility is strongly dependent on the particular sequence being inspected. In contrast, for the twist-stretch coupling it predicts values systematically lower in magnitude than any of the three AMBER variants. In terms of persistence length, all force fields tend to overestimate its value in comparison to experiments, al-

Figure 7: (a) Values of overall persistence length l_p computed for the central decamer of each sequence. The shaded region corresponds to the experimental range. (b) Contribution to the persistence length coming from generalized roll (l_p^ρ , full symbols) and tilt (l_p^τ , empty symbols), computed on the central decamer.

though CHARMM36 performs particularly well in the case of a random sequence.

An intriguing conclusion of our analysis is the dominant role played by crookedness in determining the stretch behavior of double-stranded DNA. Previous observations disclosed a mapping between the stretch modulus and the sequence-dependent conformation via the crookedness parameter, analyzing several sequences within the bsc0 force field⁴⁹. Our results not only extend this concept to the other AMBER force fields and to CHARMM36, but also show that a single mapping captures simultaneously the stretch elasticity of all force fields. Particularly, this allowed to accurately predict the sequence-dependent values of the stretching modulus in CHARMM36 by means of a mapping parameterized by using as input only the AMBER simulations, thus unveiling a common mechanism originating the different stretching response of the four force fields.

Overall, our results highlight the presence of more marked differences between the various force fields when looking at elasticity as compared to previous structural reports, whose nature varies with the specific sequence of the fragment under inspection. Yet, all the analyzed variants perform quite well in cap-

turing the elasticity of double-stranded DNA. CHARMM36 appears to be less stable than the AMBER force fields, which imposes extra cautions to be taken when analyzing DNA flexibility with simulations based on this force field. As for the AMBER force fields, the differences observed for the stretching modulus suggest that bsc1 might be preferred over OL15 for studies focused on the mechanics of dsDNA. However, due to the peculiar features of the poly-XY sequences from which this difference is argued, this observation has to be taken with caution, particularly in light of the well-known dependence of dinucleotide flexibility on the sequence of the neighboring fragments⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹. In order to conclusively determine the force field with the best performance, it would be ideal to couple the present results with single-molecule experiments on large poly-XY sequences, so as to provide the ground for a thorough and decisive comparison.

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Supporting Information Available

Convergence of simulations (S1). Step-dependent stretching stiffness (S2). Relation between changes in stretch modulus and slide (S3). Dependence of stretch modulus on water model (S4) and ionic strength (S5). Analysis of stability of simulations with CHARMM36 (S6). Anisotropy of persistence length according to global and local definitions (S7).

References

- (1) Segal, E.; Fondufe-Mittendorf, Y.; Chen, L.; Thåström, A.; Field, Y.; Moore, I. K.; Wang, J.-P. Z.; Widom, J. A genomic code for nucleosome positioning. *Nature* **2006**, *442*, 772–778.
- (2) Ong, M. S.; Richmond, T. J.; Davey, C. A. DNA Stretching and Extreme Kinking in the Nucleosome Core. *Journal of molecular biology* **2007**, *368*, 1067–1074.
- (3) Segal, E.; Widom, J. Poly (dA: dT) tracts: major determinants of nucleosome organization. *Current opinion in structural biology* **2009**, *19*, 65–71.
- (4) Marin-Gonzalez, A.; Pastrana, C. L.; Bocanegra, R.; Martín-González, A.; Vilhena, J. G.; Pérez, R.; Ibarra, B.; Aicart-Ramos, C.; Moreno-Herrero, F. Understanding the Paradoxical Mechanical Response of In-Phase A-tracts at Different Force Regimes. *Nucleic Acids Research* **2020**, *48*, 5024–5036.
- (5) Rohs, R.; West, S. M.; Sosinsky, A.; Liu, P.; Mann, R. S.; Honig, B. The Role of DNA Shape in Protein–DNA Recognition. *Nature* **2009**, *461*, 1248–1253.
- (6) Battistini, F.; Hospital, A.; Buitrago, D.; Gallego, D.; Dans, P. D.; Gelpí, J. L.; Orozco, M. How B-DNA dynamics decipher sequence-selective protein recognition. *Journal of molecular biology* **2019**, *431*, 3845–3859.
- (7) Azad, R. N.; Zafiroopoulos, D.; Ober, D.; Jiang, Y.; Chiu, T.-P.; Sagendorf, J. M.; Rohs, R.; Tullius, T. D. Experimental maps of DNA structure at nucleotide resolution distinguish intrinsic from protein-induced DNA deformations. *Nucleic acids research* **2018**, *46*, 2636–2647.
- (8) Barissi, S.; Sala, A.; Wieczór, M.; Battistini, F.; Orozco, M. DNAffinity: a machine-learning approach to predict DNA binding affinities of transcription factors. *Nucleic Acids Research* **2022**, *50*, 9105–9114.
- (9) Rohs, R.; Jin, X.; West, S. M.; Joshi, R.; Honig, B.; Mann, R. S. Origins of Specificity in Protein–DNA Recognition. *Annual review of biochemistry* **2010**, *79*, 233–269.
- (10) Chiu, T.-P.; Xin, B.; Markarian, N.; Wang, Y.; Rohs, R. TFBSshape: an expanded motif database for DNA shape features of transcription factor binding sites. *Nucleic acids research* **2020**, *48*, D246–D255.
- (11) Chiu, T.-P.; Rao, S.; Rohs, R. Physicochemical models of protein–DNA binding

- with standard and modified base pairs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2023**, *120*, e2205796120.
- (12) Dillon, S. C.; Dorman, C. J. Bacterial Nucleoid-Associated Proteins, Nucleoid Structure and Gene Expression. *Nature Reviews Microbiology* **2010**, *8*, 185–195.
- (13) Seol, Y.; Hardin, A. H.; Strub, M.-P.; Charvin, G.; Neuman, K. C. Comparison of DNA Decatenation by Escherichia Coli Topoisomerase IV and Topoisomerase III: Implications for Non-Equilibrium Topology Simplification. *Nucleic acids research* **2013**, *41*, 4640–4649.
- (14) Lee, J. Y.; Terakawa, T.; Qi, Z.; Steinfeld, J. B.; Redding, S.; Kwon, Y.; Gaines, W. A.; Zhao, W.; Sung, P.; Greene, E. C. Base Triplet Stepping by the Rad51/RecA Family of Recombinases. *Science* **2015**, *349*, 977–981.
- (15) Dziubańska-Kusibab, P. J.; Berger, H.; Battistini, F.; Bouwman, B. A.; Iftekhar, A.; Katainen, R.; Cajuso, T.; Crosetto, N.; Orozco, M.; Aaltonen, L. A., et al. Colibactin DNA-damage signature indicates mutational impact in colorectal cancer. *Nature Medicine* **2020**, *26*, 1063–1069.
- (16) Bednar, J.; Furrer, P.; Katritch, V.; Stasiak, A.; Dubochet, J.; Stasiak, A. Determination of DNA Persistence Length by Cryo-Electron Microscopy. Separation of the Static and Dynamic Contributions to the Apparent Persistence Length of DNA. *Journal of molecular biology* **1995**, *254*, 579–594.
- (17) Lipfert, J.; Kerssemakers, J. W.; Jager, T.; Dekker, N. H. Magnetic Torque Tweezers: Measuring Torsional Stiffness in DNA and RecA-DNA Filaments. *Nature methods* **2010**, *7*, 977–980.
- (18) Guilbaud, S.; Salomé, L.; Destainville, N.; Manghi, M.; Tardin, C. Dependence of DNA Persistence Length on Ionic Strength and Ion Type. *Physical review letters* **2019**, *122*, 028102.
- (19) Mazur, A. K.; Maaloum, M. Atomic Force Microscopy Study of DNA Flexibility on Short Length Scales: Smooth Bending versus Kinking. *Nucleic acids research* **2014**, *42*, 14006–14012.
- (20) Baumann, C. G.; Smith, S. B.; Bloomfield, V. A.; Bustamante, C. Ionic Effects on the Elasticity of Single DNA Molecules. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **1997**, *94*, 6185–6190.
- (21) Wenner, J. R.; Williams, M. C.; Rouzina, I.; Bloomfield, V. A. Salt Dependence of the Elasticity and Overstretching Transition of Single DNA Molecules. *Biophys J* **2002**, *82*, 3160–3169.
- (22) Herrero-Galán, E.; Fuentes-Perez, M. E.; Carrasco, C.; Valpuesta, J. M.; Carras-cosa, J. L.; Moreno-Herrero, F.; Arias-Gonzalez, J. R. Mechanical Identities of RNA and DNA Double Helices Unveiled at the Single-Molecule Level. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 122–131.
- (23) Lipfert, J.; Skinner, G. M.; Keegstra, J. M.; Hensgens, T.; Jager, T.; Dulin, D.; Köber, M.; Yu, Z.; Donkers, S. P.; Chou, F.-C.; Das, R.; Dekker, N. H. Double-Stranded RNA under Force and Torque: Similarities to and Striking Differences from Double-Stranded DNA. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2014**, *111*, 15408–15413.
- (24) Moroz, J. D.; Nelson, P. Entropic Elasticity of Twist-Storing Polymers. *Macromolecules* **1998**, *31*, 6333–6347.
- (25) Mosconi, F.; Allemand, J. F.; Bensimon, D.; Croquette, V. Measurement of the Torque on a Single Stretched and Twisted DNA Using Magnetic Tweezers. *Physical review letters* **2009**, *102*, 078301.

- (26) Gore, J.; Bryant, Z.; Nöllmann, M.; Le, M. U.; Cozzarelli, N. R.; Bustamante, C. DNA Overwinds When Stretched. *Nature* **2006**, *442*, 836–839.
- (27) Sheinin, M. Y.; Wang, M. D. Twist–Stretch Coupling and Phase Transition during DNA Supercoiling. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2009**, *11*, 4800–4803.
- (28) Gross, P.; Laurens, N.; Oddershede, L. B.; Bockelmann, U.; Peterman, E. J.; Wuite, G. J. Quantifying How DNA Stretches, Melts and Changes Twist under Tension. *Nature Physics* **2011**, *7*, 731–736.
- (29) Bryant, Z.; Stone, M. D.; Gore, J.; Smith, S. B.; Cozzarelli, N. R.; Bustamante, C. Structural Transitions and Elasticity from Torque Measurements on DNA. *Nature* **2003**, *424*, 338–341.
- (30) Lionnet, T.; Joubaud, S.; Lavery, R.; Ben-simon, D.; Croquette, V. Wringing out DNA. *Physical Review Letters* **2006**, *96*, 178102.
- (31) Mathew-Fenn, R. S.; Das, R.; Harbury, P. A. Remeasuring the Double Helix. *Science* **2008**, *322*, 446–449.
- (32) Geggier, S.; Vologodskii, A. Sequence Dependence of DNA Bending Rigidity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2010**, *107*, 15421–15426.
- (33) Lipfert, J.; Wiggin, M.; Kerssemakers, J. W.; Pedaci, F.; Dekker, N. H. Freely Orbiting Magnetic Tweezers to Directly Monitor Changes in the Twist of Nucleic Acids. *Nature communications* **2011**, *2*, 1–10.
- (34) Vafabakhsh, R.; Ha, T. Extreme Bendability of DNA Less than 100 Base Pairs Long Revealed by Single-Molecule Cyclization. *Science* **2012**, *337*, 1097–1101.
- (35) Shi, X.; Herschlag, D.; Harbury, P. A. Structural Ensemble and Microscopic Elasticity of Freely Diffusing DNA by Direct Measurement of Fluctuations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2013**, *110*, E1444–E1451.
- (36) Le, T. T.; Kim, H. D. Probing the Elastic Limit of DNA Bending. *Nucleic acids research* **2014**, *42*, 10786–10794.
- (37) Nomidis, S. K.; Kriegel, F.; Vanderlinden, W.; Lipfert, J.; Carlon, E. Twist-Bend Coupling and the Torsional Response of Double-Stranded DNA. *Physical review letters* **2017**, *118*, 217801.
- (38) Kriegel, F.; Ermann, N.; Forbes, R.; Dulin, D.; Dekker, N. H.; Lipfert, J. Probing the Salt Dependence of the Torsional Stiffness of DNA by Multiplexed Magnetic Torque Tweezers. *Nucleic acids research* **2017**, *45*, 5920–5929.
- (39) Heenan, P. R.; Perkins, T. T. Imaging DNA Equilibrated onto Mica in Liquid Using Biochemically Relevant Deposition Conditions. *ACS nano* **2019**, *13*, 4220–4229.
- (40) Jeong, J.; Kim, H. D. Determinants of Cyclization–Decyclization Kinetics of Short DNA with Sticky Ends. *Nucleic acids research* **2020**, *48*, 5147–5156.
- (41) Vanderlinden, W.; Kolbeck, P. J.; Kriegel, F.; Walker, P. U.; Lipfert, J. A Benchmark Data Set for the Mechanical Properties of Double-Stranded DNA and RNA under Torsional Constraint. *Data in brief* **2020**, *30*, 105404.
- (42) Gao, X.; Hong, Y.; Ye, F.; Inman, J. T.; Wang, M. D. Torsional Stiffness of Extended and Plectonemic DNA. *Physical Review Letters* **2021**, *127*, 028101.
- (43) Basu, A.; Bobrovnikov, D. G.; Qureshi, Z.; Kayikcioglu, T.; Ngo, T. T.; Ranjan, A.; Eustermann, S.; Cieza, B.; Morgan, M. T.; Hejna, M.; Rube, H. T.; Hopfner, K.-P.; Wolberger, C.; Song, J. S.; Ha, T. Measuring DNA Mechanics on the Genome Scale. *Nature* **2021**, *589*, 462–467.

- (44) Cruz-León, S.; Vanderlinden, W.; Müller, P.; Forster, T.; Staudt, G.; Lin, Y.-Y.; Lipfert, J.; Schwierz, N. Twisting DNA by Salt. *Nucleic Acids Research* **2022**, *50*, 5726–5738.
- (45) Lionnet, T.; Lankaš, F. Sequence-dependent twist-stretch coupling in DNA. *Biophysical journal* **2007**, *92*, L30–L32.
- (46) Liebl, K.; Drsata, T.; Lankas, F.; Lipfert, J.; Zacharias, M. Explaining the Striking Difference in Twist-Stretch Coupling between DNA and RNA: A Comparative Molecular Dynamics Analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res* **2015**, *43*, 10143–10156.
- (47) Cruz-León, S.; Assenza, S.; Poblete, S.; Guzman, H. V. In *Physical Virology: From the State-of-the-Art Research to the Future of Applied Virology*; Comas-Garcia, M., Rosales-Mendoza, S., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2023; pp 27–56.
- (48) Marin-Gonzalez, A.; Vilhena, J. G.; Perez, R.; Moreno-Herrero, F. Understanding the Mechanical Response of Double-Stranded DNA and RNA under Constant Stretching Forces Using All-Atom Molecular Dynamics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2017**, *114*, 7049–7054.
- (49) Marin-Gonzalez, A.; Vilhena, J. G.; Moreno-Herrero, F.; Perez, R. DNA Crookedness Regulates DNA Mechanical Properties at Short Length Scales. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2019**, *122*, 048102.
- (50) Dohnalová, H.; Lankaš, F. Deciphering the Mechanical Properties of B-DNA Duplex. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science* **2022**, *12*, e1575.
- (51) Luengo-Márquez, J.; Zalvide-Pombo, J.; Pérez, R.; Assenza, S. Force-dependent elasticity of nucleic acids. *Nanoscale* **2023**, *15*, 6738–6744.
- (52) Wang, J.; Cieplak, P.; Kollman, P. A. How Well Does a Restrained Electrostatic Potential (RESP) Model Perform in Calculating Conformational Energies of Organic and Biological Molecules? *Journal of computational chemistry* **2000**, *21*, 1049–1074.
- (53) Pérez, A.; Marchán, I.; Svozil, D.; Sponer, J.; Cheatham III, T. E.; Laughton, C. A.; Orozco, M. Refinement of the AMBER Force Field for Nucleic Acids: Improving the Description of α/γ Conformers. *Biophysical journal* **2007**, *92*, 3817–3829.
- (54) Noy, A.; Golestanian, R. Length Scale Dependence of DNA Mechanical Properties. *Physical review letters* **2012**, *109*, 228101.
- (55) Bao, L.; Zhang, X.; Shi, Y.-Z.; Wu, Y.-Y.; Tan, Z.-J. Understanding the Relative Flexibility of RNA and DNA Duplexes: Stretching and Twist-Stretch Coupling. *Biophysical journal* **2017**, *112*, 1094–1104.
- (56) Zgarbová, M.; Sponer, J.; Otyepka, M.; Cheatham III, T. E.; Galindo-Murillo, R.; Jurečka, P. Refinement of the Sugar–Phosphate Backbone Torsion Beta for AMBER Force Fields Improves the Description of Z- and B-DNA. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2015**, *11*, 5723–5736.
- (57) Ivani, I.; Dans, P. D.; Noy, A.; Pérez, A.; Faustino, I.; Hospital, A.; Walther, J.; Andrijo, P.; Goñi, R.; Balaceanu, A., et al. Parmbsc1: A Refined Force Field for DNA Simulations. *Nature methods* **2016**, *13*, 55–58.
- (58) Galindo-Murillo, R.; Robertson, J. C.; Zgarbová, M.; Šponer, J.; Otyepka, M.; Jurečka, P.; Cheatham, T. E. Assessing the Current State of Amber Force Field Modifications for DNA. *J Chem Theory Comput* **2016**, *12*, 4114–4127.

- (59) Huang, J.; MacKerell Jr, A. D. CHARMM36 all-atom additive protein force field: Validation based on comparison to NMR data. *Journal of computational chemistry* **2013**, *34*, 2135–2145.
- (60) Velasco-Berrelleza, V.; Burman, M.; Shepherd, J. W.; Leake, M. C.; Golestanian, R.; Noy, A. SerraNA: A Program to Determine Nucleic Acids Elasticity from Simulation Data. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2020**, *22*, 19254–19266.
- (61) Zhang, Y.; He, L.; Li, S. Temperature dependence of DNA elasticity: An all-atom molecular dynamics simulation study. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **2023**, *158*.
- (62) Minhas, V.; Sun, T.; Mirzoev, A.; Koroletov, N.; Lyubartsev, A. P.; Nordenskiöld, L. Modeling DNA flexibility: comparison of force fields from atomistic to multiscale levels. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2020**, *124*, 38–49.
- (63) Case, D.; Ben-Shalom, I.; Brozell, S.; Cerutti, D.; Cheatham III, T.; Cruzeiro, V.; Darden, T.; Duke, R.; Ghoreishi, D.; Gilson, M., et al. AMBER 2018; 2018. *University of California, San Francisco* **2018**,
- (64) Schmit, J. D.; Kariyawasam, N. L.; Needham, V.; Smith, P. E. SLTCAP: A simple method for calculating the number of ions needed for MD simulation. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2018**, *14*, 1823–1827.
- (65) Machado, M. R.; Pantano, S. Split the charge difference in two! A rule of thumb for adding proper amounts of ions in MD simulations. *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **2020**, *16*, 1367–1372.
- (66) Jorgensen, W. L.; Chandrasekhar, J.; Madura, J. D.; Impey, R. W.; Klein, M. L. Comparison of simple potential functions for simulating liquid water. *The Journal of chemical physics* **1983**, *79*, 926–935.
- (67) Joung, I. S.; Cheatham III, T. E. Molecular dynamics simulations of the dynamic and energetic properties of alkali and halide ions using water-model-specific ion parameters. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2009**, *113*, 13279–13290.
- (68) Izadi, S.; Anandakrishnan, R.; Onufriev, A. V. Building water models: a different approach. *The journal of physical chemistry letters* **2014**, *5*, 3863–3871.
- (69) Jo, S.; Kim, T.; Iyer, V. G.; Im, W. CHARMM-GUI: a web-based graphical user interface for CHARMM. *Journal of computational chemistry* **2008**, *29*, 1859–1865.
- (70) Lee, J.; Cheng, X.; Jo, S.; MacKerell, A. D.; Klauda, J. B.; Im, W. CHARMM-GUI input generator for NAMD, GROMACS, AMBER, OpenMM, and CHARMM/OpenMM simulations using the CHARMM36 additive force field. *Biophysical journal* **2016**, *110*, 641a.
- (71) Galindo-Murillo, R.; Roe, D. R.; Cheatham III, T. E. Convergence and reproducibility in molecular dynamics simulations of the DNA duplex d (GCACGAACGAACGACGC). *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-General Subjects* **2015**, *1850*, 1041–1058.
- (72) Maffeo, C.; Quednau, L.; Wilson, J.; Aksimentiev, A. DNA double helix, a tiny electromotor. *Nature Nanotechnology* **2023**, *18*, 238–242.
- (73) Roe, D. R.; Cheatham, T. E. PTRAJ and CPPTRAJ: Software for Processing and Analysis of Molecular Dynamics Trajectory Data. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2013**, *9*, 3084–3095.
- (74) Lu, X.-J.; Olson, W. K. 3DNA: a versatile, integrated software system for the analysis, rebuilding and visualization of three-dimensional nucleic-acid structures. *Nature protocols* **2008**, *3*, 1213–1227.

- (75) Frenkel, D.; Smit, B. *Understanding molecular simulation: from algorithms to applications*; Elsevier, 2001; Vol. 1.
- (76) Assenza, S.; Pérez, R. Accurate Sequence-Dependent Coarse-Grained Model for Conformational and Elastic Properties of Double-Stranded DNA. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2022**, *18*, 3239–3256.
- (77) Lavery, R.; Zakrzewska, K.; Beveridge, D.; Bishop, T. C.; Case, D. A.; Cheatham III, T.; Dixit, S.; Jayaram, B.; Lankas, F.; Laughton, C., et al. A systematic molecular dynamics study of nearest-neighbor effects on base pair and base pair step conformations and fluctuations in B-DNA. *Nucleic acids research* **2010**, *38*, 299–313.
- (78) Pasi, M.; Maddocks, J. H.; Beveridge, D.; Bishop, T. C.; Case, D. A.; Cheatham III, T.; Dans, P. D.; Jayaram, B.; Lankas, F.; Laughton, C., et al. μ ABC: a systematic microsecond molecular dynamics study of tetranucleotide sequence effects in B-DNA. *Nucleic acids research* **2014**, *42*, 12272–12283.
- (79) Dans, P. D.; Balaceanu, A.; Pasi, M.; Patelli, A. S.; Petkevičiūtė, D.; Walther, J.; Hospital, A.; Bayarri, G.; Lavery, R.; Maddocks, J. H., et al. The static and dynamic structural heterogeneities of B-DNA: extending Calladine–Dickerson rules. *Nucleic acids research* **2019**, *47*, 11090–11102.
- (80) Noy, A.; Perez, A.; Lankas, F.; Luque, F. J.; Orozco, M. Relative flexibility of DNA and RNA: a molecular dynamics study. *Journal of molecular biology* **2004**, *343*, 627–638.
- (81) Faustino, I.; Pérez, A.; Orozco, M. Toward a consensus view of duplex RNA flexibility. *Biophysical journal* **2010**, *99*, 1876–1885.
- (82) Olson, W. K.; Gorin, A. A.; Lu, X.-J.; Hock, L. M.; Zhurkin, V. B. DNA Sequence-Dependent Deformability Deduced from Protein–DNA Crystal Complexes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **1998**, *95*, 11163–11168.

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